

Ethics Form of Psychological Factors and Quality in Higher Military Educational Institutions

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Annotation:

The article describes the content of volitional qualities and scientific-theoretical aspects of the problem of volitional qualities of the influence on the self-management of a person.

Keywords: will, volitional qualities, self-control, willpower, determination, steadfastness, independence, courage, stubbornness.

ACCESS

Current volatile times in all the states cover which various different political, social and global situation no a sector apart from the rest. In particular, of the world, from countries with different the same regimen as in relation to internal threats, interstate disputes, diplomatic relations are uneven ornatish after the subscriber, as well as, extreme(emergency) situations of a nation, peaceful nations, the representatives of the effects display, in their turn, all the world, the state of confusion to put has been.

This view of point, like in times of military training of the personnel of the motherland to toe present loyalty, nation, than of mercy increase and the frontiers of our peace to keep a worthwhile contribution which will add make up, the present day state policy at the level the issue is. Our land guards extreme(emergency) cases operational decisions take whoever any situation in national taassub interaction which to choose and inner spiritual-spirit shape you make, them each how the area perfectly who know do, up the country of priority tasks, one is considered. Minion of our motherland peace provide highly responsible, the with along good work to fulfill our military participation of citizens. In them do this to patriotism, courage yeahmda determination of the qualities of enough.

THE TOPIC OF THE RELEVANCE OF

The world's current geopolitical situation and most major world powers are in tension constant on the basis of the escalation of Uzbekistan, republic of the armed forces of the military, one of the servants also combat the preparation of, also mainly also psychological qualities of the small form of quality in terms of a new level require will. This with along, of Uzbekistan, the republic of the government and the military history analysis to make of that that is, the soldiers of the availability and courage every time combat assignments in the fulfillment of the solution of the role they did not.

That is in addition to, the present day in foreign countries are different in the same situation who fall to men compared sensitivity of us, our society is also growing take in. This view point from the state of intolerance, as well as, they come to the extreme (emergency) situations to shield I stand, the land of peace, of the people in that quiet to keep the waist of the garden of military servants of nurturing every one of the state priority one of the tasks is.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

The person of the formation and development, self-management of the effects of the problem of our republic, the number of foreign scientists by scientific research was. The person self-management of the place, in the person of quality of formation and development, and this process of influence in which the factors of clarification of the problem from the get go, the number of research facilities as defined (M. Brixin [3], a. i. Visotskiy [5], Ivannikov V. A. [6], In Doubles. P. Ilin [7], V. F. Mashenko [8], The Socio S. A. [9], L. I. Ruvinskiy [12], I. V. Selivanov [13], In Doubles. K. Feshenko [14], M. V. Chumakov [15], M. Rodriguez [11], Lauvee Y., Mei, From M. [10], Davila J. Marriage [4]).

Psychology in science will understanding the definition of on a different connection could not create like quality of content analysis to make for also common, common visions of the complex available is not. In particular Krutetskiy v. a. quality content let sobitqadam, independence, determination is not, not patience, not discipline, persistence, not courage and diligence will enter [3]. Psychologist K. V. Kalin policy in accordance with in quality to classify the decision it makes. His opinion nazaricha, basal the quality of processes on the basis of being will come but this is his intellectual and moral spheres of part does not. It basal to the quality determine to mind follows the show would be chooses: activity level increase; necessary that the activity level of support; activity level and a decrease in [5, 12-b.]. Psychology science quality of the following classification of the minds separated is shown. F. n. Gonobolin quality, and you desire the action and psixik process will qo'zg'aluvchanlik and tormozlanuvchanligi with associated without 2 into groups separates [7, 56-b.]: 1-group: persistence, courage, bravery not and independence; 2-group: patience, self - self - control, endurance, discipline is not, and organizational issues will add. F. n. Gonobolin that it was noted, "every time also qualities his excitement and going to the brakes on the process, depending divide on gets. Men are some of the quality of many of the brakes, the other provoke can. It is not discipline and organizational same aspects with separated are" [7]. V. i. Selivanov also the quality of separating the main criteria make qo'zg'aluvchi, i.e. active, and tormozlanuvchan, i.e. so'ndiruvchilarga is: 1-to the group: the initiative, persistence, courage, enthusiastic and persistence; 2-group: patience, patience like quality will add [13, 142-b.].

SCIENTIFIC REVIEW

On that note it is worth, exactly, a person's of the quality of different show is: one good, one bad. That come out in case you say needless to, the will of the different situations in different show up to each.

Durability of human physiological karakterga having toe'present internal contradiction from the beginning when you forgive and it to feel that I when I start to show up will. This mental and physical work fatigue feeling by manifested toe'ladi. Some psychologists, a person's subjective feelings, the same number of fatigue to the feeling of also suspicion with a look. Also the contrast in the physiologist fatigue to the feeling of the lens condition that depending onit, depression is a feeling of with a number in into being comes. In the body, fatigue is the feeling of occurrence of the cause physiological research o'z reflected in I find.

Not determination – this person's difficulties and barriers despite the long-term for purposes of the goal towards striving in they come, the “will power”'s a long time systematically on the basis of a show up is that. Sobitqadam the physiological mechanisms of human motivational sector sustainable in ustanovkalar into being comes. That is not a determination from all ko'ra, human sobitqadamliligini otherwise has held. Determination o'ylab put the decision to a successful implementation that increased providing incredibly an important quality. Persistence of the people from a long time for no a pasaymaydigan irodaviy zo'r give and the power-the power requires makes.

Courage – various extraordinary person(extreme) cases, natural(anthropogenic) hazards, as well as in the column of the interests of others put their own interests in war, operational decision making, resulting in the effects of healthy or unhealthy fears overcome the fear of either yengmasdan stand, even if it is necessary to give the psychological feeling motivated life without risk. In general in the body, such a feature having toe'present that the person really is also strong and strong-willed is. Courage every a person with positive qualities of the one toe'become, it not only yourself and your loved ones, but also to strangers also help to give you ready to show up will. Character of such noble quality of life of any kind in the field of o'zini manifested be can:

1. **Natural disasters during.** Sometimes individuals physically strong toe'when lmas, but really too brave people, the problem is to face those who come redemption and courage that show observe, we can;
2. **In the war.** Even that, this earth on us strong, brave people and difficult times, 'do thesti to betrayal to ready the funky distinguish , we can;
3. **Daily life.** Sometimes so toe'ladi know, people risk under will be, but only a few of the help to come, and to the victim's aid give you can. Such brave people of courage owners as referred to can be.

Courage of the following types will distinguish:

- a) **Psychological** - man o'zini himself like not, its advantages and disadvantages recognize to take the ability. A man of such courage on the person's development and life strategy to sign for the opportunity it gives.
- b) **Civil** - o'zini, as well as, in the community, at work, in the community of their rights to protect to ability. Such people from others , separated stand out and o'z of the rights of protection from are not afraid.
- c) **Combat or instinktiv** - the people into this fight, to enter willingness. This is the first in the place, psychological the. Such courage ride outma be may, but it often parents in the education of their reflection will find. Ko'p something to the parents , and education participate who will all the persons are related. Courage sooner or later every one minded creatures face to come with the difficulty.

SUMMARY

Therefore, Irodaviy quality – these challenges are overcome, as well as the form of the term character with gardenliq, in certain situations manifested, which is and the person's characteristics have become irodaviy the management of self typical of a feature. Ethical and irodaviy quality of military service in the spirit of uzviylikda of incarnate o'z, in turn, them highly effective military and combat training is a bright example as it is regarded.

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